

Fiscal consequences of corporate tax avoidance by multinationals*

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Summary

1. Multinational corporations shift a large share of their profits to tax havens and, due to this corporate tax avoidance, governments lose a portion of their tax revenue.
2. We study the consequences of multinational tax avoidance on the structure of government tax revenue.
3. Using German municipal data we analyse how changes in municipal trade tax rates levied on corporate profits affect local tax revenue structure.
4. Following a trade tax rate increase, we find that municipalities with high exposure to aggressive multinationals experience a significant decline in trade tax revenue levels and shares. If they do not compensate for this decline with higher property tax rates and revenues, they experience a decline in overall tax revenues.

1. Introduction

The revelations from Panama and Paradise papers in 2016 and 2017 exposed a sizeable amount of international **tax avoidance** by firms, and in particular, **multinational corporations** (MNCs). This spurred renewed interest in the literature to calculate the extent to which MNCs shift profits to tax havens and the scale of potential tax revenue losses to governments (K. A. Bilicka, 2019; Fuest et al.,

2022; Garcia-Bernardo & Janský, 2024; Tørsløv et al., 2022).

The estimates from the literature suggest these tax revenue losses are large. In this paper, we ask **what are the consequences of these tax avoidance practices on tax revenue structure**, i.e., for where governments derive their tax revenues from if they cannot obtain them from multinationals that shift profits. To answer this question, we investigate the effects of corporate tax rate

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increases mandated by local governments on corporate tax revenues and other sources of local tax revenues. In that, we examine whether local governments offset potentially lower corporate tax revenues by raising other tax rates that they control.

2. Methods

To establish a **causal relationship between tax avoidance and tax revenue structure**, we take advantage of a large variation in municipal trade tax rates across 11,000 municipalities during the period 2008 - 2019 in Germany combined with data on the geographical presence of firms from Orbis Bureau van Dijk.

Germany provides a good laboratory to study our question, as municipalities set their own effective trade and property tax rates, while the tax bases are set by the federal government. During our sample period, the resulting effective trade tax rate varies between 7% and 21%, while the effective property tax rate varies between 3.5% and 33.6%. We specifically focus on the effects of trade tax rate changes, as this tax is levied on corporate profits and it imposes a large burden on firms. The flexibility of local governments in setting two local tax rates independently allows us to further study the complementarity between property and trade tax rates.

Our **identification strategy** relies on exploring the effects of increases in municipal trade tax rates across municipalities that are differently exposed to MNCs that can plausibly be classified as more tax aggressive. Using the event study approach, we trace the effects of those trade tax rate increases on the trade tax and overall tax revenues. As a baseline, we compare municipalities that experienced tax rate increases (treated group) to those that did

not (control group), following Fuest et al. (2018).

To understand the effect of profit shifting on tax revenue structure, we use a **triple difference-in-differences approach** in which we compare municipalities that are more exposed to aggressive MNCs and those that are not relative to the control group before and after a tax rate increase. We define aggressive MNCs as those that have at least one tax haven in their ownership structure, following the large literature, and show our results are also robust to using alternative definitions. The local exposure to more aggressive MNCs is defined as a count and a share of subsidiaries that belong to those MNCs relative to the number of all firms in each municipality.

3. Results

We find that following a trade tax rate increase at the municipal level, **the level of trade tax revenues in municipalities that are more exposed to aggressive MNCs falls**, even after controlling for trade tax rate, property tax rate, and municipal characteristics (Figure 1). We calculate the elasticity of trade tax revenues with respect to one-minus-the-tax-rate to be -0.775 for those municipalities that are more exposed to aggressive MNCs. This elasticity is in line with the elasticities from the literature that estimates the response of a firm's pre-tax profits and country tax bases to changes in tax rates to be around -1 (Beer et al., 2020).

The novelty of this paper, relative to that literature, is in **understanding the implications of profit shifting for the revenue structure**. As such, we also consider the effects of trade tax rate increases on total tax revenues and property tax rates and revenues. We find that, when municipalities

only increase their trade tax rates, they see a reduction in their overall tax revenues. When municipalities increase the property tax rates at the same time as trade tax rates, they do not experience a decline in overall tax revenues. Instead their property tax revenues also increase, which compensates for the lost trade tax revenue.

We further provide supporting evidence that in cases where the overall tax revenue declines, **municipalities also reduce their expenditures and increase debt**. We show that treated and control municipalities experience a similar evolution of tax revenue structure before the trade tax rate change, but diverge afterward, which allows us to causally interpret our findings. Further, we do not find similar effects for municipalities with a larger share of all MNCs, which we use as a placebo test.

There are **two possible mechanisms** that can explain why trade tax revenues decline after a trade tax rate increase. First, MNCs may choose to **move profits away** from municipalities that levy larger taxes on them towards their foreign locations. Given that profits are mobile across borders, this can potentially be immediately reflected in tax revenues.

Second, MNCs may choose to **move their affiliates and/or business operations** away from the municipalities that levy higher taxes on them. Further, as Bilicka et al. (2022) show, profit shifting may be accompanied by this reallocation of real operations.

Both of these effects are likely to be stronger for subsidiaries that belong to more aggressive MNCs. To disentangle the real operations from the profit-shifting mechanism, we consider the effects of trade tax rate hikes on the aggregated firm-level

real business operations of MNCs in the treated municipalities. We do not find any evidence for the real operations reallocation mechanism. As such, our results suggest that **profit shifting is driving the observed decline in the trade tax revenues**.

4. Conclusions

Our estimates suggest that **the ability of firms to shift profits affects the tax revenue structure and has potential distributional consequences**. The aggressiveness of MNCs is causally linked with lower revenue levels coming from corporations through the trade tax. As such, profit shifting affects the tax revenue structure and, in particular, the share of revenues coming from corporations.

This matters from a **policy perspective**, as it suggests that municipalities that are more exposed to profit-shifting multinationals, may choose to rely more on non-trade taxes available to them – property taxes. In fact, we show that when municipalities increase their property tax rates in conjunction with trade tax rates, there is no effect of trade tax rate increases on the overall municipal revenue, but when they only change trade tax rates, the overall tax revenue also declines.

This has two important consequences. First, to the extent that property taxation can be viewed as more regressive, **this may amplify the inequality** in municipalities that lose more tax revenue due to profit shifting. Second, imposing higher taxes to recuperate lost corporate revenues is distortionary, as it **leads to deadweight loss and reduces welfare**.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Figures

Figure 1. Dynamic Effects of the Tax Rate Increase on Municipal Revenue Structure. Source: Bilicka et al. (2024)

Note: In each panel we plot the event study coefficient estimates for the effects of trade tax rate increases for municipalities with a low share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs (low exposure munis) relative to control group and for municipalities with a high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs (high exposure munis). The high exposure to aggressive MNCs is defined as above median and the coefficients are plotted in blue diamonds, while low exposure coefficients are plotted in red circles. Each dot represents the coefficient estimate using the difference-in-differences methodology, the darker shaded box represents the 95% confidence interval, while the lighter shaded box, the 90% confidence interval. Panel (a) considers the effects on trade tax rates, Panel (b) on trade tax revenues, panel (c) on total tax revenues and panel (d) on the share of trade tax revenue in total tax revenue. In each specification we include municipality and state \times year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Further Information:

Bilicka, K. A., Dubinina, E., & Janský, P. (2024). Fiscal Consequences of Corporate Tax Avoidance. *Working Paper*. Latest version is available [here](#).

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